

Cluster Approach to Teaching English for Biology Students: Analysis of Teaching Materials

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received October 2024

Received in revised form 5

November 2024

Accepted 15 November 2024

Available online

26 November 2024

Keywords:

teaching English, cluster,
teaching materials, biology,
contextual understanding, ESP
curricula.

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of cluster-based teaching materials designed for English language instruction among biology students. Cluster approaches organize vocabulary and concepts by thematic relevance, aiming to enhance retention and comprehension of specialized terminology. Through an analysis of selected materials, the study evaluates how well these resources support language acquisition tailored to biology. Findings indicate that clustering techniques improve contextual understanding and facilitate learning by connecting biological concepts and language. The results suggest that cluster-based materials are beneficial for specialized English learning, providing a foundation for more targeted and contextually rich ESP (English for Specific Purposes) curricula.

2181-3701 / © 2024 in Science LLC

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-3701-vol2-iss6-pp72-78>

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Biologiya talabalari uchun ingliz tilini o'rgatishda klasterli yondashuv: o'quv materiallarini tahlili

Keywords:

ingliz tilini o'qitish, klaster,
o'quv materiallari, biologiya,
kontekstli tushunish, ESP o'quv
dasturlari.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqot biologiya talabalari o'rtasida ingliz tilini o'qitish uchun mo'ljallangan klaster asosidagi o'quv materiallarining samaradorligini o'rganadi. Klaster yondashuvlari maxsus terminologiyani saqlash va tushunishni kuchaytirishga qaratilgan lug'at va

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tushunchalarni tematik jihatdan tartibga soladi. Tanlangan materiallarni tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot ushbu resurslar biologiyaga moslashtirilgan tilni o'zlashtirishni qanchalik qo'llab-quvvatlashini baholaydi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, klasterlash usullari biologik tushunchalar va tilni bog'lash orqali kontekstni tushunishni yaxshilaydi va o'rganishni osonlashtiradi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, klaster asosidagi materiallar ixtisoslashtirilgan ingliz tilini o'rganish uchun foydali bo'lib, maqsadli va kontekstga boy ESP (maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili) o'quv dasturlari uchun asos yaratadi.

Кластерный подход при обучении английскому языку студентов-биологов: анализ учебных материалов

Keywords:

преподавание английского языка, кластер, учебные материалы, биология, контекстное понимание, учебные программы ESP.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье изучается эффективность учебных материалов, разработанных на основе кластеров для обучения английскому языку студентов-биологов. Кластерный подход основан на концепции тематической релевантности, что способствует улучшению запоминания и понимания специализированной терминологии. С помощью анализа отобранных материалов автор оценивает, насколько эффективны данные ресурсы для усвоения языка, адаптированного к биологическому направлению. Результаты показывают, что применение кластерного подхода улучшает контекстное понимание концепции и языка биологии. Результаты также показывают, что такие материалы в целом эффективны при специализированном изучении английского языка, обеспечивают основу для более узких и контекстуально насыщенных учебных программ ESP (английского для специальных целей).

INTRODUCTION

English proficiency is essential for biology students, given the dominance of English in global scientific research, publications, and academic discourse. A strong command of English enables students to access cutting-edge research, collaborate internationally, and effectively communicate their findings [1; 3]. However, biology students face unique challenges due to the specialized, complex terminology and abstract concepts inherent in their field. Mastery of this domain-specific language requires targeted instructional approaches that address these challenges. Thus, teaching English to biology students demands a curriculum tailored to their academic and professional needs, providing them with the language tools required for success in a globalized scientific community [2].

Biology students encounter unique challenges in learning English, primarily due to the specialized vocabulary and complex structures found in scientific literature. Unlike general English learners, biology students must grasp technical terms, Latin-derived words, and intricate descriptions of biological processes. Furthermore, scientific literature demands advanced reading comprehension skills to interpret dense, data-driven texts accurately [12]. These obstacles can hinder students' progress and limit their access to valuable scientific resources published in English. Consequently, effective English instruction for biology students requires tailored approaches that focus on vocabulary clustering, contextual learning, and strategies for navigating scientific texts, ensuring they can fully engage with global research.

The clustering method in language instruction is a technique that groups related vocabulary, concepts, or grammatical structures, enhancing retention and application [4]. By organizing information thematically, clustering aids learners in building connections between words and ideas, making language acquisition more intuitive and contextually relevant. This approach is particularly effective in specialized fields, such as biology, where students must remember and apply complex terminology. Clustered materials help students grasp these terms within meaningful contexts, improving comprehension and recall. In English for Specific Purposes (ESP), clustering supports targeted learning by presenting domain-specific language in structured, easily navigable groupings that foster deeper understanding [11].

The cluster approach is highly relevant to English for Specific Purposes (ESP), particularly for biology students, as it enables focused, context-driven learning of specialized vocabulary [14]. By organizing language into thematically related groups, the cluster approach aids students in associating terms with specific biological concepts, processes, or systems. This method not only improves retention by reinforcing connections between related terms but also enhances students' ability to apply vocabulary within meaningful scientific contexts. For biology students, who must navigate dense, technical language, the cluster approach provides a structured framework that supports both comprehension and practical usage in academic and professional settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies on English for Specific Purposes (ESP) highlight the need for tailored language instruction that addresses the specific linguistic demands of professional and academic fields [3; 5; 6; 7; 11], distinct from general English instruction, focuses on teaching relevant terminology, structures, and communication skills essential for particular disciplines, such as science, engineering, and medicine [10; 12]. Research shows that ESP instruction benefits learners by prioritizing practical language usage, preparing them for field-specific tasks, and enabling access to professional resources and collaboration [3; 8; 9; 13]. In scientific fields, where precise terminology and technical reading skills are crucial, ESP equips students with the language needed to engage with scientific literature, conduct research, and communicate findings effectively. Theoretical frameworks in ESP emphasize a learner-centered approach, adapting content to the professional and academic needs of students, thereby enhancing both motivation and outcomes [2].

"English for Specific Purposes: A Learning-Centered Approach" by Tom Hutchinson and Alan Waters (1987) emphasizes the learner-centered nature of ESP, where language instruction is tailored to specific academic or professional needs. They argue that ESP fosters relevance and engagement by focusing on subject-specific content, which is crucial for fields like science, where learners benefit from direct application of the language.

"The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes" edited by Brian Paltridge and Sue Starfield (2013) covers various ESP applications, including its role in scientific and technical fields [14]. Contributors discuss the practical importance of ESP for scientific students, noting that field-specific language instruction enables learners to effectively engage with scientific literature, understand terminology, and produce accurate written and spoken scientific communication.

"Developing Courses in English for Specific Purposes" by H. Basturkmen (2010) explores ESP course design, underscoring the importance of needs analysis to identify linguistic requirements in specific disciplines [2]. This focus is particularly pertinent for scientific students, who need skills in reading complex texts, understanding specialized vocabulary, and mastering academic writing within their field.

In "ESP in the Age of Globalization: Teaching English for Science and Technology" John M. Swales and Christine B. Feak discuss how ESP for science and technology adapts to globalization and technological advancements. They argue that, for scientific fields, ESP enables non-native English speakers to participate in global discourse, collaborate internationally, and access research findings, making language skills essential to academic and professional success in science [15].

"Specificity in English for Academic Purposes" by Ken Hyland (2002) examines distinct linguistic needs within academic English, proposing that specialized fields, like biology or engineering, require unique approaches in vocabulary and communication style. He asserts that ESP's targeted focus helps students master genre conventions and terminology, which are critical in scientific writing and presentation [11].

DISCUSSION

Existing teaching materials for teaching English to biology students often include specialized textbooks, digital resources, and supplementary tools tailored to the unique language requirements of the biological sciences. These materials typically integrate technical vocabulary, reading comprehension exercises, and writing tasks relevant to biology, designed to help students acquire both general English skills and field-specific terminology.

1. Specialized ESP Textbooks. Textbooks such as "English for Biological Science" and "English for Academic Purposes in the Life Sciences" focus on vocabulary, reading comprehension, and grammar structures essential to biology. These resources often incorporate thematic units covering topics like cellular biology, genetics, and ecology, allowing students to learn in a contextually relevant manner. Vocabulary exercises frequently emphasize clustering, where students study terms by category (e.g., anatomy, ecology), which reinforces connections between related concepts and enhances retention.

2. Scientific Journal Articles and Case Studies. Some teaching materials include authentic journal articles and case studies, introducing students to actual scientific discourse and data analysis. This exposure helps students understand the style, format, and terminology commonly found in scientific writing. Guided reading questions, vocabulary lists, and comprehension activities accompany these materials to support learning and make complex content more accessible.

3. Digital and Interactive Resources. Online platforms and apps like “English for Science” and “Oxford Learner’s Biology Vocabulary” provide interactive exercises tailored to biology students. These digital resources often include vocabulary games, flashcards, and quizzes to reinforce scientific terminology. Additionally, video lectures on biological concepts in English help students improve their listening skills while exposing them to authentic scientific language in context.

4. Laboratory Manuals and Experiment Descriptions. To enhance practical language use, some teaching materials incorporate laboratory protocols, experiment descriptions, and lab report templates. These resources guide students through structured scientific writing tasks, teaching them to describe procedures, analyze results, and write reports in a way that mirrors professional scientific communication. This hands-on approach builds confidence in using English for both written and spoken tasks within a laboratory setting.

5. Supplementary Workbooks and Academic Writing Guides. Workbooks and guides focusing on academic writing skills, like sentence structure, grammar, and punctuation, are also valuable for biology students. These materials often address common challenges in scientific writing, such as passive voice usage, technical descriptions, and presenting data. “Writing in the Biological Sciences” by Angelika H. Hofmann, for instance, provides practical exercises that help students practice writing scientific abstracts, introductions, and discussion sections [10].

Thus, the variety of teaching materials available for biology students learning English reflects a multi-faceted approach, combining vocabulary acquisition, reading and listening comprehension, and scientific writing skills. While these resources are effective, there is ongoing need for materials that fully integrate cluster-based methodologies, ensuring that vocabulary is both relevant and contextual, and helping biology students better retain and apply the English they need for academic and professional success.

FINDINGS

The cluster method offers several key benefits for biology students learning English, particularly in the areas of vocabulary acquisition, comprehension, and retention. Here are some aspects of the cluster method that seem particularly beneficial for biology students:

1. Better Understanding of Terminology. Biology students often face the challenge of mastering complex, domain-specific vocabulary. The cluster method helps by organizing related terms into thematic groups, allowing students to understand the connections between them. For example, grouping terms related to human anatomy (e.g., muscles, bones, tissues) or cell biology (e.g., mitochondria, nucleus, ribosomes) helps students contextualize each term within its biological system, rather than

memorizing isolated words. This method provides a clearer, more meaningful understanding of terminology, making it easier to grasp complex concepts.

2. Improved Retention. Clustering creates associations between education and practice, which aids in long-term retention. For biology students, it is crucial to read scientific texts and engage in academic discussions according to their specific area (e.g., terms related to genetics, ecosystems, or cellular processes) [15].

3. Contextual Learning. The cluster method promotes context-based learning by teaching vocabulary within the framework of real-world biological concepts. For example, learning about ecological systems ("habitat," "species," "food chain," and "biodiversity") can be organized in the contextual environment that ensures that biology students are not just memorizing vocabulary but are also learning how these terms function in the specific scientific discourse.

4. Application of Knowledge. The cluster method encourages students to apply learned vocabulary in practical scenarios. For example, after studying terms related to photosynthesis, students might be asked to describe the process using a set of clustered terms. This promotes active use of the vocabulary, strengthening students' ability to use the language in both written and spoken forms, which is particularly important for academic presentations, lab reports, and research discussions.

5. Increased Motivation. The cluster method makes learning more engaging for biology students because it aligns closely with their academic interests and field-specific needs. Instead of rote memorization, the clustering method offers a more logical and interesting way to learn English in the context of biology. This relevance to their field can enhance motivation, as students see direct connections between the language they are learning and their academic or professional goals.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the cluster approach is particularly beneficial for biology students learning English because it provides a structured, meaningful, and context-driven approach to mastering scientific terminology, enhancing retention, and promoting deeper understanding of both language and content. Special teaching materials (created according to cluster approach and analyzed in this research) help biology students to integrate language learning into their theoretical knowledge in the area, professional skills in practice, as well as present a valuable strategy for enhancing their language proficiency and overall academic achievement. Future research and development of cluster-based resources tailored to the evolving needs of biology students can further refine and expand the issue, ultimately bridging the gap between language learning and scientific expertise.

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